

Connecting *Terroirs*. Design Practices in the Fab City.

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Abstract

Fab City aims at fostering the social resilience of urban areas by structuring networks of Fab Labs and third-places. This research paper reviews the ontology of this initiative and provides with an understanding of the articulation between networks of interests and communities of values so to enhance Fab City's potential for territorial resilience. Openness is identified as a key feature of projects nested within Fab City, even though the diversity of participants is very low in the makers movement. In order to assess openness, this paper proposes a semiotic design methodology that is anchored in the actor-network theory and cyber-counter-culture heritage, and distancing from human-centred and participative design. The semiotic design methodology is then applied on three case studies as an illustration of the method's potential as a diagnostic tool to appreciate their openness. In providing a methodology for a systemic understanding of community oriented design, this research could help pave the way for a dynamic practice of design, one that aims at building an evolving common language for resilience while prizing cultural differences.

Keywords

fabcity, design theory, semiotic design, actor-network theory, terroirs.

1 Introduction

In 1998, the *How to make (almost) anything* class started at MIT by Neil Gershenfeld¹ initiated an educational movement aiming at empowering people by providing engineering education for everyone. In continuation of this initiative, the MIT later started the Fab Foundation NPO, formalizing a framework to widespread the form of training that had been developed by Gershenfeld in his class. The Fab Foundation fostered both the development of third places called Fab Labs and a globally distributed educational program called FabAcademy. Fab Labs were thought of as places that could and still can be proposed by anyone morally agreeing to the charter^{2,3} defined by the Fab Foundation in order to use this

¹ Professor at MIT, Director of MIT's Centre for Bits and Atoms.

² <https://www.fabfoundation.org/index.php/the-fab-charter/index.html> (consulted July 2019).

³ <http://fab.cba.mit.edu/about/fab/inv.html> (consulted July 2019).

denomination. The FabAcademy program lasts six months, is mentored by a FabAcademy alumni, and is taking place in a Fab Lab anywhere in the world.

In line with the initial ambition of empowering students, the program puts participants in the position of learning by doing, by favouring practical exercises and making activities, and encourages a form of do-ocracy - the ones that act decide. Furthermore, students are incited to make sense of the learnings on their own to their benefits, that way constructing their cosmogonies. This theoretically humanist methodology is seen as an inclusive way to widespread engineering of the world. In practice nevertheless, one can notice that the makers projects are mostly solely focused on Technics, an approach conveying a scientist bias to participants.

Fab City is a proposition originally issued by IAAC⁴, MIT's Centre for Bits and Atoms, the Fab Foundation and the Barcelona City Council and was officially launched in 2014 during FAB10, the 10th global annual reunion of the Fab Labs network. Fab City activities rely on the following hypothesis: networking Fab Labs and third places at large within a territory can help build cities that are (more) resilient. The objective is to have fully autonomous cities in terms of goods production in 2054.

Inheriting from the Fab Foundation scientist stand, discussions happening in the context of the Fab City are mostly technologically driven. The discourse is simple: if technology messed the world up, there is a way to use it so to save it. While a few researchers, such as (Kostakis *et al.*, 2015, 2016) or (Rumpala, 2014) occasionally mention the socio-political dimension of Fab City, and while many regularly recall the appropriation of production processes by citizens as the goal of the initiative, most projects and analysis remain techno-centric, focusing on how to *technically* empower participants and which *technical* objects to develop.

The challenge of Fab City is to encompass the cosmogonies of its various micro-social groups nested within a territory, negotiating the conditions for cultural expression while conferring a common vision. The goal of Fab City shall be to build new territorial traditions, also known as *terroirs*⁵. In order to achieve this, the aim of the present research is to refocus the development of Fab City as a fosterer of communities, and to propose a design methodology to help initiatives within to do so.

2 Fab City is *terroir*

2.1 A brief ontology

In 2018, the publication of the book *Fab City: The Mass Distribution of (almost) everything* (Diez, 2018) was the opportunity for a report on this young initiative. The book comprises Fab City's best practices in technological collaboration for a resilient industrial model. From blockchain (De Filippi, 2018) to artificial intelligence (Steels, 2018), through computerized ethnic patterns (Eglash, 2018), although the authors discuss the limits of technological implementation for social justice and equity, the sociological ontology of a resilient city is left aside. In an earlier discussion, the practical example of Smart Citizen – an environmental sensing electronic toolkit – is presented as a technological empowerment for citizens (Diez, 2013); the project is introduced as a means to redistribute both the power of monitoring and supposedly control over the territory by democratizing advanced technology, and enabling networking of users in a digital space. The latter prefigures how Fab City can now be identified: an initiative to redefine common grounds for citizenship, helped by technology.

We have mentioned how, in the early years of development of the Fab City initiative, the Fab Foundation has influenced it into a scientist approach. Nevertheless, the Fab City manifesto⁶ comprises

⁴ Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia.

⁵ "Terroir" is a French word that defines a territory by its ecosystem and agronomy. The term is used in this research paper as the signifier of a coherent cultural composition of a territory – by the means of crafts (know-hows), arts, and agriculture.

⁶ <https://fab.city/uploads/Manifesto.pdf> (consulted July 2019).

ten values defining the humanist stand of the community in regards to resilience: ecological, inclusive, glocalism, participatory, economic growth and employment, locally productive, people-centred, holistic, open source philosophy, experimental. A single term regards the technological inclination of the community: “locally productive”; other terms actually refer to governance (participatory, open source, ecological, glocalism), and beside the mention of economic growth, the manifesto makes it clear that the focus of the project of the Fab City is meant to be community-centred.

Furthermore, the involvement of a great variety of actors in diverse local Fab City initiatives also hints toward further socio-cultural analysis of the project. In particular, the strong involvement of the Barcelona City Council in the Fab City initiative, up to the engagement in 2014 of the team of mayor Ada Colau to make the city self-sufficient in 2054, is a sign of a socialist influence that seem as great as the scientist one of the Fab Foundation⁷.

A contradiction now appears in Fab City’s past and present influences; as scientism inherited from the Fab Foundation is stretched to the community scale, actors within are the subject of a translation of their interdependencies and activities. Scaling up the empowering idea of a Fab Lab can neither be transforming a city in a gigantic Fab Lab, neither to only focus on the question of technological availability for all. While it undoubtedly is a variable in the equation, the operations between the variables – the relations in-between human and non-human actors - are of a higher order: Fab City’s central object of discussions and research is the very design of communities.

2.2 Restating the Fab City

In the present paper, Fab City is characterized through the prism of the relations between its human and non-human actors. We can understand it as a sociotechnological network (Latour & Woolgar, 1979); the interplay of relations between its actors is based on an alignment of interests and values.

Given this, specific aspects of the Fab City manifesto become more relevant to this research: inclusive, open source philosophy, participatory. While studying the makers movement⁸, (Niaros *et al.*, 2017) identified a lack of racial and gender diversity, and a high threshold for participation, even though the maker community feeds on open resources. Pushing data and information online on expert based platforms⁹ therefore does not seem to be enough to leverage the full potential of the digital in the city, let alone trigger large-scale social inclusion.

In search for a way to foster a radical inclusion – one that is allowing and encouraging anyone to participate in the construction of the Fab City regardless of social origin, gender or race – we need to further define the notions of interests and values. As an introductory detour, anthropology provides us with extensive documentation of a paradigm similar to the one we are trying to assess: oral traditions and knowledge transfer through generations and communities. In pre-modern societies, oral traditions played a strong role in including each member of a community in its care. Oral traditions in food, architecture or crafts are commonplace since Human sedentarization. A noticeable example is the Aflaj water system in the Oman Sultanate that is over four thousand years old and still in use¹⁰. This system has a shared maintenance planning that relies only on oral traditions, and is of a great influence over the social construction of communities (Al Sulaimani *et al.*, 2007). The harsh environment of Oman triggered an articulation between a technical object (the water system), and actors within situated communities.

One of the commonalities between oral traditions and interventions within the Fab City is the presence of both a will to share practices among citizens and an attachment to a physical space. Oral traditions anchor both in a physical land and a virtual space. The virtual space comprises a set of cultural values

⁷ An interview was conducted in the framework of this research with Francesco Cingolani and Vincent Guimas (two of Fab City Grand Paris co-founders), during which the Barcelonian political influence on Fab City was discussed.

⁸ Study realized on « makerspaces », which is a term Niaros *et al.* use to gather all fabrication oriented third places such as hackerspaces or Fab Labs, for example.

⁹ Such as github.com, or wikifactory.com as examples.

¹⁰ We are displaying a single synthetic example of oral traditions as to illustrate the parallel we draw.

carried by traditions; the singularities are located physically in crafts and practices. Oral traditions are generally interpreted as the shared imaginary projection of the social structure of a given political entity (Camara, 1996), which is of interest to the one aiming at fostering situated communities. The collective and iterative design of oral tradition related crafts situates at the very core of the practice; incremental innovation of commonly shared blueprints and know-hows are an intrinsic condition to perpetuate the practice (Bauman, 1973). Crafts practices behave as amenable designs through generational and geographical relocation of knowledge, and in doing so crafts aggregate new knowledge and convey it further. The virtual knowledge base that is being conveyed by this effect is *de facto* culturally situated, it is a transmitter of values. Open source practices can be considered to happen in a similar dynamic. Furthermore, technical objects in open designs in the Fab City shall operate a transfer not of interests, but of values.

On the first hand, networks of interests are a consensual agreement between its members so to practically arrange the best conditions for each member in terms of basic needs and up to self-actualization. The social contract formed by a state typically belongs to this category. An agent within a contemporary company is expected to act as in a network of interests, where the formal contracts that are established cover an agreement of common interests¹¹.

On the other hand, communities of values are inherent to our societies; because no human organization solely relies on pure reason and interplay of interests. Religious and political groups, sports clubs or music fan clubs, to name a few, all rely on values sharing (Boltanski & Thévenot, 1991).

The aforementioned limits of the actual Fab City in regards to inclusion questions the translation of networks of interests into communities of values within the city: how can the act of design comprise values transmission and be inclusive so to transform networks into communities?

Assessing inclusion in the city is to invoke proletarianization, which straightens further the inclusive act, as facing this process is to question the expression of cultures as well as social disparities in knowledge access (Stiegler, 2012).

2.3 Introducing *terroirs*

A wide variety of initiatives are present within the Fab City: Fab Labs, makerspaces, specialized coworking spaces, but also urban agriculture and food production spaces, educational programs, various materials and electronics reuse initiatives. Although each initiative is driven by a specific set of values, most of them are shared, such as the notions of inclusiveness and open sourcing. Fab City opens a liminal *terroir*, in between the physical and the digital scapes, that is negotiating values as promoters of openness.

(Callon, 1984) proposes a mapping of networks of interests: the purpose of the exercise is to observe how the negotiation of these interests unfolds between human and non-human actors so to deliver a project. In a similar fashion, this research aims at understanding how to foster the formation of inclusive communities stemming from networks by an act of negotiation of values. As values are deeply anchored in an individual, they are hardly negotiable over the short term. Hence the methodology to foster the formation of communities would be to aggregate individuals with their specific cultural sets and values into a community that prizes their difference. The activity of “negotiation of values” – that transforms the agent of a society into a citizen that is part of a community – lies then in a semiotic effort to build a common and dynamic language and ontology. The negotiation is an act of design, or as (Zingale, 2016) puts it: “design is an act of translation”. This semiotic effort is anchored locally, in the territory, and participates in the construction of the evolving identity of the *terroir*; the semiotic activity has to make sense of the plurality of cultures by constructing a technical apparatus¹² that allows a play of

¹¹ The introduction of the “psychological contract” by Denise Rousseau (1995) proposes an understanding of how values are integrated in informal contracts in companies.

¹² The expression of the “technical object” is enlarged to “technical apparatus” so to avoid a misreading of its holiness, as it features objects, blueprints and code.

asynchronous affordances. As introduced with oral traditions, an object gains value as a cultural knowledge carrier with its capacity to incrementally aggregate new points of view over its message. The technical apparatus leaves blank spaces for users to contribute to the definition of cosmogonies, of ontologies.

The digital aspect of a technical apparatus exponentially increases its potential for cultural expression and appropriation by its users as its mobility within the design space is much higher; affordances are being almost synchronized as users can theoretically instantly share their views, and the rate of incremental improvement of the technical features and craftsmanship practices (know-hows) increases. In consequence, communities of values synchronize, mature situated practices, and generate a cultural fertilization for new meme carriers¹³ into the networks of interests. The civil society absorbs coherent memes in the terroir, which spread into communities and seed new ones.

3 Negotiation praxis

3.1 Recomposing design families

Design practices have long been challenged by post-modernist schools of thought in regards to users inclusion (“participatory design”) (Cross, 1972), and have matured towards human-centred design in the past thirty years (Cooley, 1989; Buchanan, 2001). Such practices focus on product and service design by opening the processes to final users. The emergent memetic characteristic of open designs spreading through the makers movement benefits from another heritage though. Information Technologies democratization from the 1950s, along with the development of the web in the late 1960s, facilitated the formation of a cyber-counter-culture in Western societies (Turner, 2008). This culture is characterized by the emergence of distributed communities, such as The Whole Earth Catalog illustrates (Brand, 1968-1972). It is noteworthy that the community revolving around the latter gave birth to one of the first web-based leading community of meme sharing, the WELL¹⁴. Community focused design is a practice that does not stem from human-centred design – even though it shall benefit from it, but rather from cybernetics and the way Information Technologies fostered novel approaches of the activity of values negotiation.

The keystone of a semiotic activity that aims at being inclusive by fostering the meme conveying abilities of designs is its openness. The openness defines as the wideness of the design space that is left to the actors of the network of interest so to find space for the expression of their identity in the technical apparatus. A novel design practice that is willingly focusing on openness of the designs requires its own processes, its own toolkits to foster the understanding and widespread of the practice.

Building upon the tight links structuring both linguistics and cybernetics, the present research paper proposes a semiotic design methodology as an openness measurement grid, design methodology, and flagship for the Fab City and emerging community-based practices. Four categories are identified:

- **Syntax**; the structure of the language. This is the framework of intervention.
- **Morphology**; the overall shape and scale of the various objects (signifiers) that are being stacked within the syntax.
- **Lexicon**; vocabulary, the scope of language that is being used, aggregates in a dictionary.
- **Phonology**; the accent, local specification, situated expression of the language that is transversal to the elements above.

¹³ Communities of values form and spread essentially through memes, encoded as signifiers.

¹⁴ <https://www.well.com> (consulted July 2019).

Such as the controversies mapping aiming at recovering the ontology of sociotechnological facts within networks¹⁵, the semiotic design methodology aims at building an understanding as of how to intervene to foster resilience by facilitating knowledge-based communities, and help in mapping the ways to do so.

¹⁵ <https://medialab.sciencespo.fr/fr/projets/teaching-controversy-mapping> (consulted July 2019).

3.2 Three case studies

Superilla is a tactical urbanism project led by the Barcelona City Council that was implemented in 2016. This project consists of various interventions creating new pedestrian areas and spaces for citizens by taking back streets from cars. In 2017, IAAC developed and implemented SuperBARRIO¹⁶, a gamified interface for mobile devices allowing citizens to propose designs within the Superilla areas.

The syntax, morphology and phonology of the SuperBARRIO intervention situates within the framework of Superilla, the openness does not exist as no option is left to the user but to play the game or not. It is by choosing within options of the game – the offered lexicon – that citizens are being consulted. Whereas the project is usually characterized as human-centred and participative, it does not make sense of the potential of urban negotiation of values but rather contributes to perpetuate a dominant urbanistic model – although it can surely be useful to develop citizen consultation.

Precious Plastic is a Dave Hakkens project trying to boost plastic recycling worldwide. It provides open source tools and knowledge since 2013. This project is certainly the clearest example of an evolution of design towards communities. Figure 1 illustrates partly the amount and diversity of the spread of the project worldwide. Precious Plastics headquarters are temporarily located in Eindhoven in a former industrial plant lent by the town. A worldwide interdisciplinary community meets there to work voluntarily on the development of plastic reuse machinery and usages that can be made from it.

The open distribution of machinery blueprints developed by the Dutch team of Precious Plastics allows for the amenability of machinery designs, which translates as a situated local specification of the syntax (technical improvements, scaling, various material usage, for example). As the latter is dynamic, the morphology and vocabulary – which are composed by the usages and design spaces of the reused plastic productions – are left very opened: whatever the way, plastic pollution needs to be assessed in any way. An interesting feature of the project is the fact that the phonology impact falls short as the vocabulary is almost limitless; what does it mean for a language to have accents if they are by definition already part of the dictionary?

¹⁶ <http://superbarrio.iaac.net> (consulted July 2019).

Figure 1 – Screen capture of “preciousplastics” research on Instagram.

Volumes Coworking is a Parisian space founded in 2015 by three architects, featuring a food lab and a makerspace. Daily activities focus mainly on architectural topics such as computational design and vernacular constructions conferences, participative urbanism trainings and workshops. Experts in residence cross paths with local communities thanks to an open programation of events. Francesco Cingolani (co-founder of Volumes) makes sense of the emerging activities as a platform democratizing the use of advanced digital tools such as those one can find in a makerspace. Removing the technicality of such innovations from the everyday discourse with local communities, while encouraging them to visit by hosting proximity services and open events, Volumes is offering to participate to a novel paradigm inherited from cyber-counter-culture.

Barriers to entrance are dramatically lowered to facilitate participation in the project of Volumes. As an experimental space, the morphology (typology of space usage here) is left very open. One could even see the peculiarity of the presence of the foodlab within a space dedicated to architecture as a bold choice to widen the design space. The intrinsic feature of architectural design confers Volumes with a rather closed syntax, although the phonology diversity is encouraged. The latter is especially noticeable considering the consolidation of the relationships the space has with the neighbouring communities over time.

4 Discussions

This research paper aims at providing new design research opportunities for Fab City, making sense of its identity and positioning. In acknowledging the humanist stand that the initiative takes over the scientist vision of the Fab Foundation, Fab City could develop further projects in that direction so to achieve its goal of fostering social resilience. A key feature of its approach is the open source philosophy; developing further the tools to do so in the sense radical inclusion would mean to challenge current practices in that field. Open source current practices consist in pushing information on specialized web platforms, and are sometime facilitating their use by providing tutorials. The lack of diversity in the making communities as pointed out by Niaros *et al.* is a consequence of such barriers to entrance; benefiting from open source too often means to already be part of the community. Acknowledging a

new design methodology focusing on semiotics, not directly inheriting from human-centred design practices and interfaces, but focusing on communities by valuing the contributions from social sciences, could be beneficial in enhancing the potential of the open source philosophy. The proposed semiotic design methodology was used in the present research paper as a reading guide for openness qualitative appreciation. As a design methodology, numerous developments are foreseeable: a community designer could use it all along a project to assess critical design decisions – while taking part in a “design for resilience” community. The methodology is then a flagship as it calls for its own improvement and has the potential of providing critical thinking to designers willing to challenge dominant social models and deconstruct neo-colonialist ones.

An archaeology of the future would eventually read our epoch as the one of worldwide cultural collage that attempted to face environmental issues together, rather than one of Western scientism.

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References

- Al Sulaimani, Z., Helmi, T., & Nash, H. (2007). The Social Importance and Continuity of Falaj Use in Northern Oman. *International History Seminar on Irrigation and Drainage*. doi:<http://hdl.handle.net/10036/15174>
- Bauman, Z. (1973). *Culture as Praxis*. Routledge & K. Paul.
- Boltanski, L., & Thévenot, L. (1991). *De la justification. Les économies de la grandeur*. Paris: Gallimard.
- Brand, S. (1968-1972). *The Whole Earth Catalog*.
- Buchanan, R. (2001). Human Dignity and Human Rights: Thoughts on the Principles of Human-Centered Design. *Design Issues*, 17(3), 35-39. Récupéré sur <http://www.jstor.org/stable/1511799>
- Callon, M. (1984). Some elements of a sociology of translation: domestication of the scallops and the fishermen of St Brieuc Bay. (J. Law, Éd.) *The Sociological Review*, 32(Power Action and Belief A New Sociology of Knowledge), 196-233.
- Camara, S. (1996). La tradition orale en question. (É. d. l'EHESS, Éd.) *Cahiers d'Études africaines*, 144, pp. 763-790. doi:10.3406/cea
- Cooley, M. (1989). Human-centred Systems. (H. Rosenbrock, Éd.) *Designing Human-centred Technology*, 133-143.
- Cross, N. (1972). *Design participation: proceedings of the Design Research Society's conference, Manchester, September 1971*. London: Academy Editions.
- De Filippi, P. (2018). Blockchain. *Fab City: The Mass Distribution of (almost) everything*, 26-31.
- Diez, T. (2013). The Fab and the Smart City. The use of machines and technology for the city production by its citizens. *TEI*, (pp. 447-454). Barcelona. doi:10.1145/2460625.2460725
- Diez, T. (2018). *Fab City: The Mass Distribution of (almost) everything*. (T. Diez, Éd.) Barcelona: Institute for Advanced Architecture of Catalonia.
- Eglash, R. (2018). Decolonizing Digital Fabrication. *Fab City: The Mass Distribution of (almost) everything*, 44-59.
- Kostakis, V., Niaros, V., Dafermos, G., & Bauwens, M. (2015). *Design global, manufacture local: Exploring the contours of an emerging productive model* (Vol. 73). Futures. doi:10.1016/j.futures.2015.09.001
- Kostakis, V., Roos, A., & Bauwens, M. (2016). Towards a political ecology of the digital economy: Socio-environmental implications of two competing value models. *Environmental Innovation and Societal Transitions*, 18, 82-100. doi:10.1016/j.eist.2015.08.002

- Latour, B., & Woolgar, S. (1979). *Laboratory life : the social construction of scientific facts*. Beverly Hills: Sage Publications.
- Niaros, V., Kastakis, V., & Drechsler, W. (2017). Making (in) the smart city: The emergence of makerspaces. *Telematics and Informatics*, 1143-1152.
- Rousseau, D. (1995). *Psychological Contracts in Organizations: Understanding Written and Unwritten Agreements*. SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Rumpala, Y. (2014). « Fab labs », « makerspaces » : entre innovation et émancipation ? *Revue internationale de l'économie sociale*, 85-97. doi:10.7202/1027278ar
- Steels, L. (2018). Artificial Intelligence and Urban Community Memories. *Fab City: The Mass Distribution of (almost) everything*, 32-43.
- Stiegler, B. (2012). *États de choc: Bêtise et savoir au XXIème siècle*. Fayard/Mille et une nuits.
- Turner, F. (2008). *From Counterculture to Cyberculture. Stewart Brand, the Whole Earth Network, and the Rise of Digital Utopianism*. University of Chicago Press.
- Zingale, S. (2016). Design as translation activity: a semiotic overview. (P. Lloyd, & E. Bohemia, Éds.) *Proceedings of DRS 2016, Design Research Society 50th Anniversary Conference*, 1061-1072.